

METHODS OF ASSESSING THE LEVEL OF DIGITAL LITERACY OF SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN A DIGITAL LEARNING ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *One of the key elements of digitization of education is digital literacy. Digital literacy is a key priority of education, which includes designing and using content using digital technologies, computer programming, graphic techniques, computer programming, graphic visualization techniques, computer graphics, multimedia development of online courses, etc., information retrieval. and sharing is the ability to communicate with others.*

Keywords: *digital literacy, digital technologies, computer literacy, media literacy, visualization.*

Methods of assessing the level of digital literacy of secondary school students in a digital learning environment.

Improving the system of personnel training in the field of information technologies is one of the important conditions for the successful implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" strategy, the development of digital technologies and the wide implementation of them in the everyday life of the population, and it is defined as an urgent task and is being implemented in the educational process.[1]

One of the key elements of digitization of education is digital literacy. Digital literacy is a key priority of education, which includes designing and using content using digital technologies, computer programming, graphic techniques, computer programming, graphic visualization techniques, computer graphics, multimedia development of online courses, etc., information retrieval. and sharing is the ability to communicate with others.

Digital literacy is a set of knowledge and skills necessary for safe and effective use of digital technologies and Internet resources. Everything can be solved with information competences. Developing skills to use and create content using digital technologies, including searching and sharing information, answering questions, communicating with other people, and working with computer programs. [2] In order to develop the digital skills of students, there is a need to assess their level of digital literacy. In the assessment, attention should be paid to the following components:

- information literacy;
- computer literacy;
- media literacy;
- communicative literacy;
- positive attitude to technological innovations.

These components or indicators are evaluated against each of the following aspects: knowledge (cognitive aspect), skills (technical aspect), attitude (ethical aspect) Knowledge is

modern man describes theoretical ideas about the importance of information in society, the possibilities of digital technologies and the principles of computer hardware and software operation, etc. Skills determine a person's ability to successfully work with information using digital technologies. Attitudes reflect a person's attitude to ethical standards in working with information and communication technologies and how much he follows these rules. Thus, each component of digital literacy is evaluated in terms of the listed aspects. In order to assess the digital literacy of secondary school students, it is recommended to conduct an online survey using the Google Forms platform as follows:

1. Information literacy:
 - I have an understanding of the role of information in human life;
 - I can search for information from available resources on the Internet;
 - I can distinguish between useful and useless information.
2. Computer literacy:
 - I have an understanding of computer devices;
 - I can use the computer independently;
 - I can use the computer purposefully.
3. Media literacy:
 - I understand the diversity of information sources, forms and channels of its distribution;
 - I can search for information from various sources, verify their reliability and completeness;
 - I can take a critical approach to news and informational messages.
4. Communicative literacy:
 - understand the difference between digital and live communication;
 - I can use modern means of communication;
 - I know the terms of ethics and morality in the digital environment.
5. Positive attitude to technological innovations:
 - I understand new technologies;
 - I am ready to work with new and modern technologies-applications, gadgets;
 - I understand that technological innovations are useful for the development of oneself and society

Through the analysis of this questionnaire, it will be possible to determine the level of digital literacy of students, such as finding information, working with digital devices, using modern digital communication tools, the ability to study media materials (analysis and criticism), and their attitude to new technologies.[3]

Summary. Changes in the digital educational environment associated with modern digital technologies have a rapid impact not only on the development of scientific knowledge, but also on the improvement of pedagogical and psychological knowledge in education. It is important to assess the digital literacy of students and develop their digital skills based on the analysis of the obtained results in the implementation of modern digital technologies in education and increasing the efficiency of their use.

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